

RECOMMENDED LEGAL AND LICENSING TERMS FOR YOUR DATA

Option A:

CC0

WITH ATTRIBUTION REQUEST

“This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by [CC0 1.0](#). Attribution is requested.”

Recommended for:

- Organizations developing new data policies
- Those willing to share their data freely to maximally reduce friction in use

What it is:

- CC0 is not a license; it dedicates data to the global public domain
- We add attribution requests by default, although they are not legally required

Benefits:

- Enables distribution, remixing, and adaptation without legal restrictions
- Encourages professional attribution
- Eliminates legal complexities, releasing any burden on users

Considerations:

- Address sensitive data proactively before sharing in the public domain
- Manage the use of name trademarks if necessary

Option B:

CC BY 4.0

“This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0.”

Recommended for:

- Producers and publishers that want to share and still own their copyrightable data, where allowed

What it is:

- CC BY is a highly permissive license that allows unrestricted reuse as long as proper attribution is given

Benefits:

- Retains data ownership in permitting jurisdictions
- Offers a legal mechanism for enforcing attribution and proper data use
- Could provide a way to track data use via attributions

Considerations:

- Sharing can become complex when users want to merge with other licensed data
- May not apply in all jurisdictions or on non-copyrightable material

RECOMMENDED METADATA VALUES FOR YOUR DATA

(TABLE 1: ABOUT YOUR DATA)

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
<p><u>ABOUT MY DATA/DATABASE/PRODUCT</u></p> <p><i>My organization has published something and made it available to share with you, and we want to make sure you attribute it to us and our sources. These metadata values provide information for sharing, attribution, and provenance.</i></p>	Title	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
	Publisher	Korea Meteorological Administration
	Identifier	doi:XXXXXXX/kma.domain
	License	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
	Rights Statement	CC0 with Attribution Request. This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CC0, which allows users worldwide to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse. Attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to include this information easily.
	Bibliographical Citation	Korea Meteorological Administration, Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Issued 2004-01-01, Modified 2004-03-01, doi:XXXXXXX/kma.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0 , CC0 with Attribution Request

RECOMMENDED METADATA VALUES FOR YOUR DATA

(TABLE 2: ABOUT YOUR SOURCES)

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
<p>ABOUT MY SOURCE(S)</p> <p><i>My organization got data from other sources, and we want to make sure we attribute our sources. These metadata values provide information for sharing, attribution, and provenance.</i></p>	Source 1 Title	KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
	Source 1 Publisher	Climate Data Store (CDS)
	Source 1 Identifier	doi:XXXXXXXX/cds.domain
	Source 1 License	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
	Source 1 Bibliographical Citation	KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Climate Data Store, doi:XXXXXXXX/cds.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0 , CC0 + Attribution Request; Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Korea Meteorological Administration, doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0 , CC0 + Attribution Request
	Source 2 Title	Japanese Land and Water Levels 2003
	Source 2 Publisher	Japan Meteorological Agency
	Source 2 Identifier	doi:XXXXXXXX/jma.domain
	Source 2 License	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
	Source 2 Bibliographical Citation	Japanese Land and Water Levels 2003, Japan Meteorological Agency, doi:XXXXXXXX/jma.domain, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/ , CC BY 4.0.